

COMMUNICATIVE METHODS OF COMMUNICATION WITH STUDENTS

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Abstract. *One of the important factors which shows teacher`s professional skill is teacher`s talent of communicating with his students. Especially his oral effecting through word embodied in teacher`s communicating talent, his talent of encountering will be basement on his achieving success on educational – upbringing activity. In the following article different ideas relying on pedagogical experiences are given about oral effecting through word on the base of teacher`s speech talent.*

Keywords: *teacher, communicative tasks, educational-influencing model, fascination, accuracy.*

INTRODUCTION, LITERATURE REVIEW AND DISCUSSION

For a teacher who systematically analyzes his pedagogical practice, the awareness of communicative tasks as the main instrumental component confirms how important it is, how clear the educational-impacting model is, the fascination, accuracy, clarity of the impact itself. Let's pay attention to the everyday communication of people. Imagine you have to ask a stranger something. Naturally, the main method is to ask. However, before speaking directly about what is asked, you should strive to organize the initial situation that ensures success. In this case, politely organize the psychological environment using well-known communicative methods, master the object in communication, and then directly carry out the impact. Each influencing technique used in the classroom, in the process of communicating with the team, must have exactly the same communicative teaching. As a result of a survey conducted with teachers of various pedagogical experience, the following was revealed: many of them, despite the fact that they systematically apply pedagogical means, do not recognize communicative tasks as a necessary important element of the pedagogical process. In this, almost all teachers are well aware of such components as the selective system of educational methods and the pedagogical impact for the systematic implementation of their pedagogical tasks. Despite the fact that the teacher can quite successfully answer the question "What should be done in case of emergency?", Doubting it, he thinks when answering the question "How to implement it?". In order to answer this question, it is necessary to clearly define the logic and methods of the system of communication with students. In the methods used in the pedagogically acting methodology applied in the activities of A.S. Makarenko, in many cases, having precisely determined the goal in education and upbringing, one can see the establishment of the correct organization of the situation when communicating European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol. 8 No. 4, 2020 ISSN 2056-5852 Progressive Academic Publishing, UK Page 129 www.idpublications.org with students. In some cases, a kind of "face-to-face attack" shows the possibility of awareness of communication, which provides an opportunity to understand what's the matter and without direct communication of the teacher with the foster child, the system of official conversation at meetings or joint holding of various events with the class staff, which every student is capable of. Among the effective pedagogical methods used by the teacher in the educational process, in particular the method of

collective and individual conversation, is of great importance. However, the effectiveness of using these methods and situations that arise in the process of communication can be different. It is these methods that ensure the effectiveness of the impacting methods in the educational process. The establishment of communicative methods used in the performance of pedagogical tasks has always been a difficult problem. Especially young teachers are keenly aware of these difficulties in the initial years of their activity. The teacher fulfills communicative tasks - it comes from various forms of pedagogical activity, the formed level of the classroom team, the principles of communication management, the individual age characteristics of students who are participants in the situation. The ratio of the communicative task to the pedagogical task, the comparison of the communicative task of the chosen methodology with the educational impact and the organization of their unity provides the process of communication and generally pedagogical mutual cooperation. In this regard, the following connection can be traced: firstly, the methodology of working with a classroom team is mediated with the communication system, and secondly, the ways of solving current communicative tasks of communication are determined by the strategy of the methodology of the chosen pedagogical impact. A future teacher can master the basics of professional and pedagogical communication in pedagogical educational institutions, during a stormy pedagogical activity, as well as in the process of self-education. In this, the teacher should know in detail the following important communicative tasks: Communicative tasks that the teacher should know

- 1 Know in detail the laws, system and principles of studying the continuous processes of professional and pedagogical communication.
- 2 Systematically master the order and technologies of the direct use of pedagogical communications in the educational process.
- 3 Continuously master the skills of professional pedagogical communication.
- 4 Systematically develop communication skills.

European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol. 8 No. 4, 2020 ISSN 2056-5852 Progressive Academic Publishing, UK Page 130 www.idpublications.org It is considered incorrect that these areas will fully provide the process of mastering the professional communication skills of a teacher. The systematic correlation of the general creative positions with their professional pedagogical activity of communication, the definition of their system, logic, optimal individual forms are considered an inevitable condition for activity leading to the mastery of pedagogical communication. And also, the teacher should test his theoretical rules of pedagogical communication in his experiments. How does a teacher carry out communicative tasks, and what functions does he perform in the educational process? The fact that communicative tasks are multifaceted in pedagogical activity, the teacher feels good. For a long time you can continue the list of tasks that help in solving such pedagogical problems of communicative tasks as mutual cooperation with students during education and upbringing, accustom students to perform some kind of community work, build relationships between team members, and provide the necessary emotional microclimate. Communicative communication of a teacher is a system that has many functions:

- information and communication;
- regulatory and communicative;
- affective-communicative.

In the process of performing communicative tasks, these functions should be carried out in a full, integrated manner, otherwise the effectiveness of the teacher's communication with students will decrease and will not produce the intended results. Young teachers who are just starting their professional activities are required to master comprehensive in-depth knowledge for constant

introspection, effective pedagogical preparation for the lesson process. In particular, - have in-depth knowledge of their subject and thoroughly know the material being studied; - seriously prepare for pedagogical, psychological and methodological communication with students; - to study the internal psychological characteristics of each student and class team; - freely behave when communicating and hold your mental and psychological emotions; - master professional skills and communication skills with a cool team; - be able to demonstrate the highest examples of pedagogical culture and pedagogical tact, to develop pedagogical intelligence and worldview; - be able to draw up a technological map of classes based on the criterion for the selection of methods and means corresponding to the goal, objectives and content of subjects; - knowingly knowing pedagogical situations that are occurring accidentally and be able to apply drastic measures in relation to them. The success of teacher training in communicating with students largely depends on the ability of the teacher to master and apply communication skills. An important component of professional pedagogical communicative communication is the teacher's ability to clearly express his thoughts and reasoning, emotional feelings. When a teacher is angry at various random pedagogical situations, rejoices, resents, experiences, like an actor, he must be able to find a way out of one position to another, from one form to another. In this sense, the famous Russian teacher A.S. Makarenko in his works as follows sets out his thoughts about the professional qualities of a teacher: "A teacher in a lesson cannot but play a certain peculiar role. A teacher who does not know how to play a role in the classroom scene European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol. 8 No. 4, 2020 ISSN 2056-5852 Progressive Academic Publishing, UK Page 131 www.idpublications.org cannot conduct professional activities. He is, in a sense, an actor. It is absolutely unacceptable that our behavior, disposition, character are for us a pedagogical weapon. We cannot allow the upbringing of children with the help of our emotional experiences, feelings. After all, we are people. If in other various professions it is possible to solve the problem without spiritual zeal, then the teacher should conduct activities without mental pain. The student sometimes has to show emotional pain in communication. For this, the teacher must also be able to play a positive role, like an actor on the stage. However, one should not play a stage role superficially. In this game there is some kind of belt connecting the teacher with his amazing personal ability, this is a role that demonstrates your excellent behavior. This stage game is not some kind of a dead accident or a technique, but a real process that shows hidden spiritual feelings, kindness. " In a certain sense, a teacher in his pedagogical activity is distinguished by his psychological experience, peculiar qualities that differ from the natural feelings of carriers of other professions. It should be noted that the teacher, while fulfilling his communicative tasks, along with the bearers of other professions lives under various environmental influences and in the mainstream of human feelings, and the originality of his professional activity is manifested in this, the teacher's feelings and feelings must correspond to the pedagogical goal. In the process of the teacher performing communicative tasks, the pedagogical impact that occurs due to the pedagogical activity, feelings, emotions, and concerns of the teacher is a combination of the teacher's complex life and purposeful concerns; it is in this process that the set of vital, beyond voluntary concerns associated with the teacher's professional activities is preserved. As a result, the teacher's experience in pedagogical situations also creates a sense of responsibility towards their activities regarding pedagogical arbitrariness. Therefore, beyond arbitrary cares are carried out on the basis of feelings aimed at the teacher's arbitrary chores and pedagogical educational goals.

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